

Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud

CALL	<p>Ministry of University and Research (MUR), Directorate-General for Internationalization and Communication, Notice D.D. 3264 dated 28/12/2021.</p> <p>Mission 4 "Education and Research" - Component 2 "From research to enterprise" - Investment Line 3.1 "Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructure", Action 3.1.1 "Creation of new IRs or strengthening of existing ones that contribute to Horizon Europe's Scientific Excellence objectives and networking"</p>
PROJECT TITLE	Humanities and cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud
PROJECT ACRONYM	H2IOSC
PROJECT ID	IR0000029
PROJECT WEBSITE	https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it
CUP	B63C22000730005
WP	WP1 "Project and Financial Management, Quality Assurance"
OU	OU 1 OVI-CNR
DELIVERABLE NUMBER	1.5
DELIVERABLE TITLE	H2IOSC Forum Report
EXPECTED DELIVERY DATE	30/04/2025
ACTUAL DELIVERY DATE	31/10/2025
<p>This project is funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU. The views and opinions expressed are only those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.</p>	

AUTHOR(s)

Organization	Name	Contact information
CNR-OVI	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	emiliano.deglinnocenti@cnr.it
CNR-ISPC	Veronica Colautti	veronica.colautti@cnr.it
CNR-OVI	Alessia Spadi	alessia.spadi@cnr.it
CNR-OVI	Irene Falini	irene.falini@cnr.it
CNR-ISPC	Cristina Massi Benedetti	cristina.massibenedetti@cnr.it

ABSTRACT

D1.5 is a practical resource to understand and consolidate the project's acquired knowledge, offering valuable support to the Project decision-making structure in achieving project objectives. The primary objective of D1.5 is to assess the implementation conditions of the H2IOSC project across various thematic issues, including: i) activities of the RIs nodes; ii) connection and effective implementation of policies and guidelines defined by the federation; iii) synergies with other relevant actors; iv) coordination and management of facilities, tools and services; v) definition and implementation of strategic documents (business models, networking activities, technology and skills transfer, outreach); vi) monitoring and evaluation activities.

This version provides an updated state of the art of the Project as well as the outline of the KPIs defined for each dashboard so to have a complete view of H2IOSC implementation conditions.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF ACRONYMS

LIST OF FIGURES

LIST OF TABLES

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and Project Overview

1.2 Participating Infrastructures

1.3 Building the H2IOSC Federation

1.4 Project Structure

1.5 H2IOSC Shared Goals: Key Activities, Key Exploitable Results

1.6 Purpose and Objectives of the Deliverable

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Approach and framework for assessing implementation conditions

2.2 Data collection and analysis methods

3. PROPOSED SOLUTIONS

3.1 Overview of proposed solutions and strategies to address identified issues

- 3.1.1 Infrastructure Node Performance Dashboard
- 3.1.2 Policy and Guideline Compliance Dashboard
- 3.1.3 Partnership and Networking Performance Dashboard
- 3.1.4 Facilities, tools and Services Management Dashboard
- 3.1.5 Strategic Development and Collaboration Dashboard
- 3.1.6 Performance Measurement and Assessment Dashboard

3.2 Description of actors involved and the expected impact on implementation conditions

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5. UPDATES AND CONTINUOUS MONITORING

LIST OF ACRONYMS

A	Activity
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
D	Deliverable
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ERA	European Research Area
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FOE	Fondo Ordinario per gli Enti e le istituzioni di ricerca
GLAMs	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums
H2IOSC	Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud
ICT	Information and communications technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KA	Key Activities
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MUR	Ministero dell'università e della ricerca
OPERAS	Open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities
OU	Operational unit
OVI	Opera del Vocabolario Italiano
PNIR	Piano Nazionale per le Infrastrutture di Ricerca
PNR	Piano Nazionale della Ricerca
PNRR	Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza

RI	Research Infrastructure
SSH	Social Sciences & Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure number	Figure name
1	H2IOSC Territorial Nodes (DCs)
2	WPs Interrelations
3	Shared Objectives, Key Exploitable Results, Key Activities

LIST OF TABLES

Table number	Table name
1	Targeted Research Infrastructures (RIs)

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and Project Overview

H2IOSC (Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud¹) is a project coordinated by the Italian Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche and designed to create a federated and inclusive cluster of 4 Research Infrastructures (RIs) in the ESFRI domain of Social and Cultural Innovation, to enable researchers from various disciplines in the fields of humanities, language technologies and cultural heritage to collaborate in research by sharing tools, services and data.

1.2 Participating Infrastructures

H2IOSC foresees the collaboration of the Italian nodes of 3 ESFRI Landmarks in Social and Cultural Innovation **CLARIN**², **DARIAH**³, **E-RIHS**⁴ and the project **OPERAS**⁵

In the table below a brief description of each participating RI is provided, according to Part 3 of the ESFRI Roadmap 2021⁶:

RI Name	ESFRI Roadmap Description
CLARIN	The Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN) is a distributed Research Infrastructure that provides easy and sustainable access for scholars in the Humanities and Social Sciences to FAIR digital language data – in written, spoken or multimodal form – and advanced tools to discover, explore, exploit, annotate, analyze or combine them, independent of their location. CLARIN is building a networked federation of language data repositories, service centres and centres of expertise, with single sign-on access for all members of the academic community in all participating countries. Tools and data from different centres are interoperable, so that data collections can be combined and tools from different sources can be chained to perform complex operations to support researchers in their work. Entered in the ESFRI Roadmap 2016, CLARIN became a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2012. Since several countries have joined either as full Member, or as Observer. The ultimate goal is to include all European countries as well as any interested third countries in or outside Europe. Most operations, services and centres of the CLARIN infrastructure are provided and funded by CLARIN Members (and Observers). They set up a national consortium, typically consisting of universities, research institutions, libraries and public archives, of which at least one has the status of CLARIN Centre which is expected to create and provide access to digital language data collections, and digital tools and expertise for researchers to work with them.
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) is a distributed Research Infrastructure to enhance and support digitally enabled

¹ See: <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it> (last checked 27.02.2024)

² See: <https://www.clarin.eu/> (last checked 27.02.2024)

³ See <https://www.dariah.eu/> (last checked 27.02.2024)

⁴ See: <https://www.e-rihs.eu/> (last checked 27.02.2024)

⁵ See: <https://operas-eu.org/> (last checked 27.02.2024)

⁶ See: <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/> (last checked 27.02.2024)

	<p>research and teaching for Arts and Humanities. DARIAH is a network of people, expertise, information, knowledge, content, methods, tools and technologies from its member countries. It develops, maintains and operates an Infrastructure that sustains researchers in building, analyzing and interpreting digital resources. By working with communities of practice, DARIAH brings together state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities and scales their results to a European level. It preserves, provides access to and disseminates research that stems from these collaborations and ensures that best practices, methodological and technical standards are followed. Entered in the ESFRI Roadmap 2006, DARIAH was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2014. DARIAH was awarded Landmark Status in 2016 as a Research Infrastructure that reached its Implementation Phase and was considered a pan-European hub of scientific excellence. Currently, DARIAH has 20 Members, one Observer and several Cooperating Partners in six non-member countries. Structurally, DARIAH operates through the Europe-wide networks of the Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs) and their constituent Working Groups. Each of the four VCCs is cross-disciplinary, multi-institutional, international and centred on a specific area of expertise. Within this structure, DARIAH has over 20 dynamic Working Groups to integrate national services under specific operational categories.</p>
E-RIHS	<p>The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) is a distributed Research Infrastructure to support research on heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation and management. E-RIHS delivers integrated access to expertise, data and technologies through a standardized approach, and integrate world-leading European facilities into an organization with a clear identity and a strong cohesive role within the global heritage science community. Through interdisciplinary access to the four platforms – E-RIHS ARCHLAB, E-RIHS DIGILAB, E-RIHS FIXLAB, E-RIHS MOLAB – E-RIHS supports a wide variety of research, from smaller object-focused case studies to largescale and longer-term collaborative projects, and stimulates innovation in instrumentation, portable technologies and data science. The long-term tradition of this field of research, the ability to combine science with innovation, and the support provided by EU-funded projects and integrating activities such as EUARTECH, CHARISMA, IPERION CH and IPERION HS in conservation science, and ARIADNE in archaeology, represent the background of E-RIHS. Entered in the ESFRI Roadmap 2016, E-RIHS was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2025. It offers access to a wide range of fixed and mobile instruments in national facilities of recognized excellence, physically accessible collections/archives and virtually accessible heritage repositories for standardized data storage, analysis and interpretation.</p>
OPERAS	<p>The OPen scholarly communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities (OPERAS) is a distributed RI to enable Open Science and upgrade scholarly communication practices in the Social Sciences and Humanities in line with the EOSC. OPERAS pools resources and offers services to enable all SSH stakeholders to streamline their activities and maximize the</p>

	<p>societal impact, in an interdisciplinary, mission-driven approach. OPERAS fosters the co-creation and adoption of scholarly communication services addressing research needs in terms of discovery, content creation, quality assurance, dissemination, outreach, and evaluation of outputs. It catalyses knowledge and know-how sharing, practices adoption, and increases return on socio-economic investments. The OPERAS Concept and Design Phase dates back to 2012- 2018 when the coordinated actions to establish the network and shaping the project began. This effort leads to the recognition of OPERAS as a project addressing High strategic potential area for research in SCI in the ESFRI Roadmap 2018. OPERAS started its Preparation Phase in 2019 by developing the business plan and governance model and promoting services creation and alignment for EOSC catalogue and transnational access. In 2019, OPERAS established the status of International non-profit Association under Belgian law (AISBL). Entered the ESFRI Roadmap 2021, OPERAS is striving to efficiently guarantee an efficient move to the Operation Phase with a coherent approach to technical, administrative, and financial issues and the establishment of OPERAS ERIC.</p>
--	--

Table 1. Targeted Research Infrastructures (RIs)

The activities of the Italian national nodes for the above RIs are coordinated by CNR institutes, namely: CNR-OVI (DARIAH), CNR-ISPC (E-RIHS), CNR-ILC (CLARIN) and CNR-ILIESI (OPERAS). The strategic role of each national node is represented by the “High Priority” label awarded by the Italian Ministry for University and Research (MUR) in the context of the Italian National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures (Piano Nazionale per le Infrastrutture di Ricerca – PNIR). The PNIR is the Italian strategic program aimed at promoting the creation, expansion, and enhancement of research infrastructures in the country. PNIR is managed by the Ministry of University and Research (MUR) and aims to improve the accessibility and quality of Italian research infrastructures, fostering collaboration between institutions and promoting international participation.

PNIR focuses on various research areas, including humanities and social sciences and aims to provide the scientific communities of reference with advanced equipment, such as laboratories, high-performance computing centers, specialized research facilities, scientific data archives, and other resources necessary to conduct high-quality research.

Through PNIR, the Italian government seeks to promote competitiveness and excellence in national research, as well as attract and retain talented researchers. The program also supports collaboration between public and private research institutes, universities, businesses, and other stakeholders in the scientific and technological sector.

PNIR is a long-term initiative that involves planning, resource allocation, and monitoring of research infrastructures in Italy. The goal is to create an environment conducive to internationally recognized research and contribute to the country's economic growth and scientific advancement.

The daily operations of the said national nodes are supported by specific funding measures granted annually to CNR by MUR (Fondo Ordinario per gli Enti e le istituzioni di ricerca – FOE).

The FOE is, however, not sufficient to allow financial sustainability for the H2IOSC federation and/or its resources and should be only considered as one of the funding channels available.

1.3 Building the H2IOSC Federation

The H2IOSC project is part of a long-term strategy developed by the Department of Humanities, Social Sciences & Cultural Heritage of the CNR, with the aim of building a federated Italian infrastructure for Open Science in the SSH research sector, a digital ecosystem with FAIR resources, services and tools for researchers, professionals in the Creative and Cultural industry and citizens.

The H2IOSC marketplace is a one stop platform enabling access to advanced tools, services and resources for conducting innovative and computationally intensive research on complex digital with a strong focus on multidisciplinary and will be interoperable with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)⁷ and the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud.

H2IOSC brings the collaboration among the Italian nodes of CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS to the next level by seeking to foster the accessibility of available resources and reduce the fragmentation of the SSH digital ecosystem through the creation of a National Cloud as well as with the definition of shared practices, standards, processes and tools for data collection, mapping, modeling, transformation and management.

Through the enhancement and federation of Italian nodes of the four high-priority research infrastructures, H2IOSC develops a network of high-performance computing nodes connected at high speeds to the Italian research network.

These nodes provide shared services for the creation, management, retrieval, and reuse of open and interoperable digital resources and processes, including data, tools, and digital objects provided by participating infrastructures or produced by researchers.

⁷ See: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en (last checked 27.02.2024)

Figure 1. H2IOSC Territorial Nodes (DCs)

H2IOSC also establishes customizable digital laboratories dedicated to cutting-edge research in various disciplines, including linguistics, art history, archaeology, and cultural heritage sciences. These laboratories leverage technologies such as virtual and augmented reality, artificial intelligence, and big data analysis.

Through extensive collaborations with universities, libraries, archives, museums, and other organizations, the project involves the scientific community in its activities, ensuring that their needs are considered through the entire H2IOSC implementation phase.

H2IOSC has an innovative potential which lies in the multidisciplinary collaboration between high-tech sectors such as computer science, data science, and artificial intelligence with a vast range of disciplines within the humanities and the cultural heritage sector.

In the long run, H2IOSC's ultimate challenges are: supporting the digital turn in the SSH by fostering open science and open data and providing access to a FAIR ecosystem of digital resources; promoting the development of innovative sustainability models for RIs in the Social and Cultural Innovation ESFRI landscape; implementing a strategy to enhance the potential of new generations of researchers, by improving their skills and expertise through doctoral scholarships with high scientific and technical competence.

1.4 Project Structure

The H2IOSC project structure follows an iterative and incremental development strategy and is divided into eight Work Packages (WPs), each serving a unique role and bringing tangible results to the federation (see below, Section 1.5 H2IOSC Shared Goals: Key Activities, Key Exploitable Results, for further details):

- **WP1 “Project and Financial Management, Quality Assurance”** is focused on guaranteeing the achievement of work program objectives, milestones, and deliverables while staying within budget constraints (see below, Section 2.1 Approach and framework for assessing implementation conditions, for further information).
- **WP2 “Landscaping & building communities”** creates a catalogue of various resources (e.g., projects, tools) relevant in the H2IOSC scientific domain and assess their degree of FAIRness and digitization, in view of their integration which takes place in **WP3**. Furthermore, WP2: identifies gaps, missing tools and environments to be developed as pilots and innovative services, in **WP7**; creates an inventory of best practices, standards, to be supported by appropriate training in **WP8**; identify the user needs in terms of storage, processing, tools and software to be provided in **WP3** and **WP6**; identifies stakeholders (communities of reference, public actors, relevant projects) to be targeted, in collaboration with A1.5, and identifies priorities for the resources and tools to include in the national marketplace in **WP5**.
- **WP3 “Digital Resources Standardization, Consolidation & Alignment”**, assesses the technological maturity level of resources (refer to WP2) according to the entry point threshold established by the project, i.e., “Technology Readiness Level” (TRL). The layer of interoperability needed for the RIs federation is done in **WP4**.
- The main outcome of **WP4 “RIs Nodes and Resources Interoperability”** is to create interoperability between the repositories of the IRs by offering an information model that allows the integration of records from highly diversified single IRs into a common vision (common semantic framework). Furthermore, WP4 designs and implements the cluster of datacenters, that is the physical infrastructure of the H2IOSC federation. This WP is strongly related to each of the other WPs.
- The aim of **WP5 “Marketplace”** is to establish and build the framework for the H2IOSC Marketplace. This online tool is designed to enhance the visibility of data sources, services, and resources offered by RIs and the broader research community. The Marketplace is hosted in the H2IOSC National Cloud, ensuring full compliance with the FAIR principles. The H2IOSC Marketplace relies on resources that have been evaluated for their TRL and assessed as candidates for inclusion by the participating RIs. The H2IOSC validation framework, to be designed in **WP3**, is based on the criteria described in WP5.
- The focus of **WP6 “Resources Accessibility: Servification, Virtualization, Remotization”** centers around the processes of servification, virtualization, and remotization of current tools and services offered by the participating RIs. Regarding Servification and Virtualization, involved RIs carry out refactoring and re-engineering tasks for existing tools and services, providing uniform and unified access to researchers and scientific communities. Regarding remotization, WP introduces

protocols for remote-controlled measurements performed in situ with scientific instrumentation.

- The developments provided by **WP5** and **WP6** and their innovation potential are validated in the **WP7 “Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments”**. Its objective is to define and implement a series of innovation-oriented services and proof-of-concept sets of resources for direct use by researchers in the form of Pilot applications hosted on the H2IOSC platform.
- The goal of **WP8 “Training, Capacity Building, Engagement”** is to equip user communities with both interdisciplinary and domain-specific skills and competencies in FAIR and Open Science. Additionally, it aims to provide training on the offerings of disciplinary infrastructures at both national and international levels. Based on the output of **WP2**, the common and domain specific policies aim at identifying the training needs, the communities to be targeted, and the types of intervention to be classified.

Overall, the project structure of H2IOSC is designed to ensure effective communication, coordination, and integration of resources, while addressing different levels of complexity and achieving the project's goals in the field of humanities, cultural heritage, and heritage science.

Figure 2. WPs Interrelations

1.5 H2IOSC Shared Goals: Key Activities, Key Exploitable Results

In the context of H2IOSC, the Shared Goals are defined as “the desired outcomes that the project aims to achieve to reach its scientific and technological objectives, for which the progression of all the activities outlined in the technical annex is crucial” (see above, Section 1.4 Project Structure). In general terms the overall goal for H2IOSC is to federate the Italian nodes of E-RIHS, CLARIN, OPERAS and DARIAH, and create a unified and interoperable

ecosystem where researchers, scholars, professionals and citizens, can access data, services, tools and other resources related to the Humanities and Cultural Heritage.

A core set of Shared Goals for the H2IOSC federation - directly stemming from the project overall goal - includes:

1. The **Joint Resources Catalogue** of H2IOSC resources;
2. The **network of Data Centers** representing the backbone of the H2IOSC distributed infrastructure providing resources enabling researchers from various disciplines to collaborate effectively in data- and compute-intensive research;
3. The **Marketplace**, an online platform that increases the visibility and utilization of data sources, services, and resources provided by the Research Infrastructures (RIs) and the broader research community. The Marketplace follows the FAIR principles, ensuring data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable;
4. The enhancement of the services provision capabilities, through the development of a **Service Oriented Infrastructure**, exposing services developed and maintained by the participating infrastructures and/or the federation;
5. The **Scientific Pilots**: platforms or hubs bringing together services and interfaces to support specific (domain based) scientific workflows. The pilots designed to be scalable and extendable, accommodating new resources and data as the implementation progresses;
6. The **training resources and platforms**: online learning environments where users can access training materials, resources, and courses related to FAIR and Open Science principles, as well as the use of research infrastructures. The platforms provide a range of training modules and courses tailored to different disciplines and levels of expertise.

Figure 3. Shared Objectives, Key Exploitable Results, Key Activities

For each Shared Goal, we can identify a Key Exploitable Result (KER), a tangible outcome defined as: “significant outcome(s) or output(s) that holds potential for further exploitation. It could be a tangible piece of knowledge, technology, or innovation that can be further developed, translated into practical applications, and ultimately create economic or societal value)”.

The Shared Goals are closely linked to the Key Exploitable Results through the Key Activities, which are the means to accomplish those goals. The relation between these three components can be described as follows:

1. Shared Goal: **Joint Resources Catalogue** of H2IOSC resources.
 - Key Activities: Development and implementation of a standardized cataloging system, harmonization of metadata, integration of resources from different domains and research infrastructures.
 - Key Exploitable Result: A comprehensive and searchable catalogue of H2IOSC resources that enables researchers to discover and access relevant data, services, and resources across different disciplines and infrastructures.

2. Shared Goal: Network of **Data Centers** representing the backbone of the H2IOSC distributed infrastructure.
 - Key Activities: Establishment and interconnection of data centers, development of data management and sharing protocols, provision of scalable computing resources.
 - Key Exploitable Result: A robust and interconnected network of data centers that provides researchers with the necessary infrastructure and resources to collaborate effectively on data- and compute-intensive research projects.

3. Shared Goal: **Marketplace** for increased visibility and utilization of data sources, services, and resources.
 - Key Activities: Design and development of an online platform, integration of data sources and services, adherence to FAIR principles for data discoverability and accessibility.
 - Key Exploitable Result: An online Marketplace that serves as a central hub for researchers to find, access, and utilize various data sources, services, and resources, fostering collaboration and enabling the reuse of research outputs.

4. Shared Goal: Enhancement of service provision capabilities through a **Service Oriented Infrastructure**.
 - Key Activities: Development of a service-oriented architecture, integration and exposure of services from participating infrastructures, establishment of a federated infrastructure.
 - Key Exploitable Result: A Service Oriented Infrastructure that enables seamless access and utilization of services provided by the participating research infrastructures, improving the overall service provision capabilities.

5. Shared Goal: **Scientific Pilots** as platforms or hubs for domain-based scientific workflows.

- Key Activities: Design and development of scalable and extendable pilot platforms, integration of services and interfaces, accommodation of new resources and data.
 - Key Exploitable Result: Scientific pilot platforms that bring together domain-specific services and interfaces, supporting researchers in executing specific scientific workflows and facilitating collaboration across disciplines.
6. Shared Goal: **Training resources and platforms** for FAIR and Open Science principles.
- Key Activities: Development of online learning environments, creation of training materials and modules, customization for different disciplines and expertise levels.
 - Key Exploitable Result: Training platforms that provide researchers with access to educational resources and courses on FAIR and Open Science principles, promoting the adoption of best practices and enhancing users' skills and competencies.

In a nutshell, the path from Shared Goals to Key Exploitable Results involves defining Key Activities that lead to the execution of specific actions within the project. These activities ultimately generate tangible results that align with the Shared Goals and have the potential for further exploitation, creating economic or societal value. This entire process is at the core of the H2IOSC operation and implementation conditions and will eventually impact the definition of a sound strategy (among other things) for the project's Value Proposition and Sustainability. For this reason is crucial to monitor the process with specific tools, such as Dashboards (see below, Section 1.6 Purpose and Objectives of the Deliverable) and other tools tracking progress, evaluating performance, facilitating decision-making, promoting transparency, managing risks, and ensuring effective documentation and reporting. These tools should provide a comprehensive and visual overview of the project's implementation, enabling stakeholders to optimize resource allocation, address challenges, and ultimately maximize the project's value proposition and sustainability.

1.6 Purpose and Objectives of the Deliverable

According to the Technical Annex: “D1.5 is the output of A1.5 and will consist of a set of documents assessing the implementation conditions of the H2IOSC project, providing to the Project Manager and the decision-making structure insights related to different thematic issues that may represent a bottleneck as well as suggesting pragmatic solutions to deliver on time and within budget”. Based on the context described in the previous sections, “the path from Shared Goals to Key Exploitable Results”, is “at the core of the H2IOSC operation and implementation conditions” and should be carefully monitored, using specific tools.

As described in D1.1 and further explained in the following paragraphs (see, Section 2.1, point 6, Monitoring and Evaluation) H2IOSC is already using a number of tools for monitoring and reporting, which, however, should be integrated to fully exploit the potential of the acquired knowledge, and offer support to the Project decision-making structure in achieving the scientific objectives set out in technical annex (i.e. the Shared Goals).

Thus D1.5 plays a vital role in the H2IOSC project. It encompasses a comprehensive set of recommendations that will help and support the evaluation of the project's implementation

conditions. The primary objective of D1.5 is to provide the Project decision-making structure with valuable insights concerning thematic issues that may pose bottlenecks to the progress towards the Shared Goals, including, but not limited to:

- Overseeing the operations of the RIs nodes;
- Ensuring the adherence and successful execution of policies and guidelines set by the federation;
- Facilitating collaboration with other pertinent stakeholders;
- Streamlining coordination and management of facility, tool, and service development or enhancement;
- Providing assistance in defining and implementing business models, while encouraging networking, outreach, and technology and skills sharing;
- Assisting in the monitoring and evaluation of activities.

Furthermore, this deliverable supports the elaboration of possible pragmatic solutions aimed at ensuring the achievement of the project objectives (i.e. the Shared Goals) organized in dashboards, with the following focuses:

- Infrastructure Node Performance Dashboard
- Policy and Guideline Compliance Dashboard
- Partnership and Networking Performance Dashboard
- Facilities, tools and Services Management Dashboard
- Strategic Development and Collaboration Dashboard
- Performance Measurement and Assessment Dashboard

A dashboard is a visual interface that provides an overview of relevant information and key performance indicators in a clear and concise manner, allowing users to monitor and track specific aspects of a system or process.

The dashboards mentioned work by aggregating and displaying real-time data and insights related to the respective activities (i.e. Key Activities). They present metrics, trends, and visualizations that enable users to assess the performance, compliance, partnerships, management, strategic development, and overall effectiveness of the corresponding areas within the federation. Users are able to access and interpret the information presented on the dashboards to make informed decisions, identify areas of improvement, and ensure efficient and effective operations towards the achievement of the Shared Goals and the actual delivery of the Key Exploitable Results.

2. Methodology

2.1 Approach and framework for assessing implementation conditions

As stated before WP1 "Project and Financial Management, Quality Assurance" is primarily focused on ensuring the successful achievement of the Project's objectives, milestones, and deliverables while maintaining adherence to budget constraints. It also plays a crucial role in establishing effective communication channels and managing external interactions between the Project and various stakeholders, particularly the Ministry of University and Research (MUR). One of the key responsibilities of WP1 is to establish project agreements and ensure

compliance with the rules and reporting requirements set by the ministry and PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan).

A significant objective of WP1 is the establishment of a decision-making framework, as detailed in Section 4 (Decision Making) of D1.1 (Quality assurance plan, guidelines, project handbook)⁸. This framework is designed to facilitate prompt and coordinated communication between the actors involved in H2IOSC, as described in Section 3 of D1.1⁹, including Operative Units (OUs) and Research Infrastructures (IRs), enabling efficient decision-making processes within the project to ensure the achievement of the Shared Goals.

Moreover, WP1 takes on the responsibility of clearly defining accountability across all levels of the project. This ensures that everyone involved in the project understands their specific roles and responsibilities, promoting efficient collaboration and effective execution of tasks.

A shared governance structure is crucial to ensure the achievement of Shared Goals and facilitate the path from Shared Goals to Key Exploitable Results. It promotes alignment, collaboration, strategic decision-making, resource mobilization, monitoring, accountability, stakeholder engagement, and long-term sustainability. A well-functioning shared governance structure enhances the project's effectiveness, relevance, and overall impact.

In this context Task 1.5 "Forum: promoting shared governance for the H2IOSC federation", plays a crucial role in setting up the optimal conditions to provide practical assistance to the decision-making structure of the H2IOSC project. This task encompasses several key responsibilities, including:

- 1) **Monitoring RIs Activities:** Task 1.5 involves monitoring the activities of the Research Infrastructures (RIs) nodes within the project. This includes tracking their progress, ensuring compliance with project guidelines, and identifying any potential issues or obstacles. This activity is undertaken (initially) in close collaboration with WP4 which is the responsible for setting up the H2IOSC territorial nodes, and then extended to other WPs, to include and represent all the relevant Key Exploitable Results (see above, Section 1.5: H2IOSC Shared Goals: Key Activities, Key Exploitable Results).
- 2) **Implementation of Policies and Guidelines:** It is responsible for ensuring the connection and effective implementation of policies and guidelines established by the federation. This helps maintain consistency and coherence across the project, promoting unified decision-making processes. This activity is undertaken in close collaboration with WP3 which is the responsible for setting up the H2IOSC digital resources alignment and policies framework, and then extended to the other WPs (i.e. WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP8) to include all the relevant frameworks and policies elaborated by the federation.
- 3) **Synergies with Relevant Actors:** Task 1.5 promotes synergies with other relevant actors in the field. This involves establishing collaborations and partnerships with external entities to leverage their expertise, resources, and networks for the benefit of

⁸ Cfr.: D1.1 *Quality assurance plan, guidelines, project handbook*, pp. 15-17.

⁹ Cfr.: D1.1 *Quality assurance plan, guidelines, project handbook*, pp. 11-13.

the H2IOSC project. This includes strengthening collaborations (i.e.: the ITSERR¹⁰ and FOSSR¹¹ PNRR-IR projects, presented within the same call and the CHANGES¹² project, presented within the Extended Partnerships call n.5) as well as other collaborations (i.e. the FAIR¹³ project, presented within the Extended Partnerships call n. 1), to improve the synergistic action between H2IOSC and its participating RIs and other actors and provide infrastructural support for the planned research and innovation actions (i.e. in the case of PE5, CHANGES).

- 4) **Coordination and Management of Facilities, Tools, and Services:** It facilitates the coordination and management of the development or upgrade of facilities, tools, and services within the project. This ensures smooth integration and operation of various components required for the project's success. Leveraging on the work being done for point 1) Monitoring RIs Activities, several key sub-tasks and responsibilities are planned and undertaken to achieve the desired outcomes: i) Facility Development and Upgrades: this sub-task involves planning, coordinating, and overseeing the development or upgrade of facilities required for the H2IOSC project. It includes identifying the infrastructure needs, ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and standards, and managing the construction or modification process; ii) Tool Development and Enhancement: this sub-task focuses on the coordination and management of the development or enhancement of tools necessary for the project's implementation. It includes identifying the specific requirements, collaborating with relevant stakeholders, managing the development process, and ensuring the integration of the tools into the project workflow; iii) Service Provision and Management: this sub-task involves the coordination and management of the services provided within the H2IOSC project. It includes defining service requirements, establishing service-level agreements, monitoring service delivery, and addressing any issues or challenges that may arise; iv) Integration and Interoperability: this sub-task focuses on ensuring the smooth integration and interoperability of various components within the project. It entails identifying interfaces and integration points, coordinating communication and data exchange between different systems, and resolving any compatibility issues; v) Operational Efficiency and Optimization: this sub-task aims to improve the operational efficiency of facilities, tools, and services within the project. It involves implementing best practices, streamlining processes, optimizing resource utilization, and continuously monitoring performance to identify areas for improvement.
- 5) **Business Models and Networking:** Task 1.5 supports business models within the project (D1.4 *Sustainability Financial Plan*). It also encourages the development of networking activities, outreach initiatives, and technology and skills transfer to foster collaborations and maximize the impact of the project. This activity is crucial for

¹⁰ Cfr.: <https://www.itserr.it/>

¹¹ Cfr.: <http://www.fossr.eu/>

¹² Cfr.: <https://sites.google.com/uniroma1.it/changes/home>

¹³ Cfr.: <https://www.fondazione-fair.it/>

elaborating the value proposition of the project (i.e.: elements representing the unique added value of the H2IOSC cluster) and facilitating its long-term success and support the creation of a sustainable and profitable framework to capitalize on the project's outcomes, technologies, and expertise. Outreach activities are also essential for raising awareness about the H2IOSC cluster and its value proposition. By engaging with potential customers (users), both from the public and private sectors, WP Leaders contribute to identifying the target audience for each key activity. This understanding helps tailor the services and offerings to meet specific needs and interests, ensuring a customer-centric approach. Leveraging on the work being done for point 1) Monitoring RIs Activities, in the preparation of a comprehensive list of possible activities and services that the H2IOSC cluster can offer to third parties (i.e. the Key Exploitable Results), this process also involves identifying potential sources of revenue, exploring regional/national and international contributions, as well as considering fees for the services provided (where possible and within the borders set up by the national and international rules and regulations). Researchers and key personnel are involved in the analysis of possible revenues, ensuring a thorough assessment of the financial aspects included in H2IOSC Deliverable 1.4 *Sustainability Financial Plan*.

- 6) **Monitoring and Evaluation:** This sub-task provides support for monitoring and evaluation activities within the H2IOSC project, as described in sections 5 (Monitoring) and 6 (Reporting) of D1.1¹⁴. This includes assessing the progress, identifying potential challenges, and collecting valuable data to inform decision-making processes. According to D1.1 Section 5 (Monitoring) in consideration of the Project's ambitions and articulation and due to the short time range available for its implementation "the integration of different monitoring activities" is required "for the successful execution of the H2IOSC activities plan"¹⁵. Thus this sub-task is the most suitable to host activities linked to integration of existing tools and elaboration of means to provide "an overview of relevant information and key performance indicators in a clear and concise manner, allowing users to monitor and track specific aspects of a system or process" (i.e.: Dashboards).

Task 1.5 thus designs a centralized data platform, providing real-time insights into various aspects of the project's implementation and outcomes, allowing stakeholders, including the Project decision-making structure, to monitor the project's performance against predetermined targets (i.e.: Shared Goals). The platform is fed with information gathered in the above sub-tasks, that will be captured (see the section on data collection for further details) and integrated to provide representations presenting the data in a user-friendly and easily understandable format.

¹⁴ Cfr.: D1.1 *Quality assurance plan, guidelines, project handbook*, pp. 19-31.

¹⁵ Cfr. D1.1 *Quality assurance plan, guidelines, project handbook*, p. 19.

2.2 Data collection and analysis methods

In consideration of the project's Shared Goals, Key Activities and Key Exploitable Results, to collect the necessary information within H2IOSC, the project's internal organization and the participating Research Infrastructures (RIs) development agenda has been leveraged. This involves the following steps:

- a. **Data requirements identification:** Within each Work Package, the project team identifies the specific data and information needed to monitor and evaluate the progress and performance of the Key Activities related to that package. This could include key performance indicators (KPIs) and metrics that are used to measure success.
- b. **Data collection mechanisms:** The project team collaborates with the participating RIs to establish data collection mechanisms. This may involve setting up data reporting processes, implementing data tracking systems, or leveraging existing data management (or reporting) systems within the RIs. The goal is to ensure the regular and systematic collection of relevant data points.
- c. **Integration of development agenda:** The project team aligns the data collection efforts with the participating RIs' development agenda. This means integrating the monitoring and reporting requirements into the RIs' ongoing activities and processes. The development agenda of the RIs serves as a framework for defining the specific data points and indicators that need to be collected.
- d. **Data analysis and reporting:** The collected data are analyzed and processed to generate meaningful insights and reports. This analysis helps in assessing the performance, compliance, and progress of the activities within the project and the participating RIs towards the achievement of the Shared Goals. The results are presented through the dashboards mentioned earlier, providing a clear overview of the project's status and highlighting areas that require attention or improvement.

3. Proposed Solutions

With the aim of designing and implementing specific tools (i.e. Dashboards) to monitor “the path from Shared Goals to Key Exploitable Results”, leveraging on existing monitoring and reporting tools, processes and systems and reducing the fragmentation of the current situations, we proposed a methodology to assess H2IOSC implementation conditions (i.e.: “the path from Shared Goals to Key Exploitable Results”, see Section 2.1 above) and a process to collect and analyze the collected data (Section 2.2 above), both within the context of Task 1.5 activities. In the following paragraphs we provide an overview of possible specific tools (i.e.: Dashboards) to monitor and assess the project’s performance. The proposed dashboards, described in the following paragraphs, should be considered as examples and their coverage and scope should be refined through collaborative design within the project.

Furthermore, the implementation of the dashboards should be considered a mid to long term goal for the project rather than a short-term endeavor. There are several reasons why this implementation requires adequate time and planning. First and foremost, since developing a comprehensive set of dashboards integrating data from various sources and systems within the project involves having clear requirements and data collection mechanisms already in place. This requires a thorough understanding of the data landscape, data mapping, and data integration processes. It may involve consolidating data from disparate systems, ensuring data quality and consistency, and establishing robust data pipelines. This integration process can be complex and time-consuming, requiring careful planning and coordination.

Considering these factors, the implementation of the dashboards should be viewed as a mid to long term goal for the project. Adequate time should be allocated for planning, development, stakeholder engagement, data integration, and iterative refinement. By taking a comprehensive and phased approach, the project can ensure the successful implementation and adoption of the dashboards, ultimately enhancing project management, decision-making, and the overall success of the H2IOSC project.

3.1 Overview of proposed solutions and strategies to address identified issues

3.1.1 Infrastructure Node Performance Dashboard

The Infrastructure Node Performance Dashboard is a specialized tool designed to monitor and assess the performance of the Research Infrastructures (RIs) nodes involved in the H2IOSC project. It serves as a centralized platform that provides comprehensive insights into the activities, achievements, and challenges of each RI node within the project.

This dashboard enables stakeholders, project management, RIs coordinators, and decision-making structure, to track and evaluate the performance of individual RI nodes against predefined benchmarks and key performance indicators (KPIs). It offers a holistic view of the nodes' contributions to research and innovation, their collaborative efforts, and their adherence to project objectives (i.e.: § 1.5 “H2IOSC Shared Goals: Key Activities, Key Exploitable Results”).

Furthermore, the Infrastructure Node Performance Dashboard facilitates collaboration and knowledge exchange among the nodes. It highlights successful partnerships, joint research endeavors, and shared resources, enabling stakeholders to identify and leverage synergies

between the nodes. This promotes collaboration and enhances the overall impact of the project. Through the dashboard, stakeholders can assess not only operational performance but also the broader effectiveness and impact of the activities carried out by each RI node.

The dashboard also helps identify challenges and areas for improvement within each RI node. It allows stakeholders to identify potential bottlenecks, resource allocation issues, or capacity gaps that may hinder the node's performance. By providing clear insights into these challenges, stakeholders can take proactive measures to address them and optimize the performance of each node.

Overall, the Infrastructure Node Performance Dashboard plays a vital role in monitoring, evaluating, and optimizing the performance of the RI nodes within the H2IOSC project. It offers stakeholders a comprehensive overview of each node's activities, achievements, and challenges, facilitating evidence-based decision-making and ensuring the successful implementation of the project. Through this dashboard, stakeholders can effectively assess the progress and impact of the RI nodes, foster collaboration, and drive continuous improvement in research and innovation within the field of humanities and cultural heritage.

Key Performance Indicators:

KPI Number of users served by each RI node

Indicator	Number of users served by each RI node
Definition(s)	This KPI measures the total number of user access events associated with the services offered by each RI node.
Rationale	The KPI monitors the utilization of services and how access is distributed across different modes of interaction
Assumptions	It is assumed that all services are clearly mapped and categorized by the RI nodes, and that access to each service can be recorded consistently.
Data/information needs and resources	This KPI is informed by structured service mapping activities conducted within the project.
How is the KPI calculation carried out	The total number of access events to services is aggregated from the available datasets. Access events are reported separately by category, allowing for analysis by type of user interaction.
Who is providing this information	Provided by RIs
Sources	internal service usage records; project logs
Unit of measure	Number

The measured KPI values are reported below.

The investigated data concerns the number of accesses given on an annual basis (2024) by the nodes for the services foreseen in WP6 and the number of accesses given as H2IOSC cluster, for the same services, through the TNA/NA calls (1-2-3) for which details are available at the following link: <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/tna-na-calls/>

Service name	node name	access number (per node)	access number (TNA calls H2IOSC)
ATON (WebXR services for HS)	E-RIHS.it	15300 (public accesses worldwide in 2024)	9
Kapto (capture services)	E-RIHS.it	440 (national)	1
SENSE - Wireless sensor networks for cultural heritage conservation and monitoring	E-RIHS.it	0	2
GATTO	DARIAH-IT	2000	NA
TIGRO	DARIAH-IT	2000	1
MFE: MetaFAIR Ecosystem	DARIAH-IT	100	1
DPH - Digital Philology Hub	DARIAH-IT	100	NA
LexO ItAnt	CLARIN-IT	4 (linked to EpiLexO ItAnt)	NA
CASH ItAnt	CLARIN-IT	4 (linked to EpiLexO ItAnt)	NA
SKOSMOS Vocabulary Service	CLARIN-IT	0	1
EpiLexO Editor ItAnt	CLARIN-IT	50	18
eScriptorium	CLARIN-IT	100	13
EpiLexO Editor	CLARIN-IT	4	NA
Federated Content Search	CLARIN-IT	300	NA

It is also important to consider the role of the H2IOSC Marketplace. As the Marketplace will become fully operational only at the end of the project, it is not possible to provide meaningful

data on user access through this platform, the figures available at this stage would be not representative of its actual use.

Once the Marketplace is fully functional, the corresponding KPI should include access events both through the Marketplace and directly via the individual Research Infrastructures (RIs).

KPI Research Output Efficiency

Indicator	Research Output Efficiency
Definition(s)	Indicates the level of research activity and the volume of scientific output generated within the H2IOSC Federation by the 4 RIs
Rationale	For the purposes of this KPI, a publication is defined as any formally shared research output that contributes to the dissemination of knowledge and results arising from the use of Research Infrastructure (i.e.: articles featured in scientific journals but also publications on Zenodo). The timeframe to be considered is the duration of the project. Publications produced within the timeframe of the project but not yet published by its end can also be considered if properly mapped in the project logs (e.g: article accepted by a journal which will be published after the end of the project)
Assumptions	Research outputs have been mapped throughout the project
Data/information needs and resources	To compute this KPI, each RI node must collect metadata on research outputs
How is the KPI calculation carried out	The KPI is calculated by counting the research output produced within each RI node.
Who is providing this information	Provided by RIs
Sources	Deliverables; Project logs
Unit of measure	Number

The measured KPI values are reported below.

The data investigated concern the number of publications carried out from the beginning of the project until 31 October 2025, prepared by the individual nodes and the H2IOSC cluster, including for example deliverables, articles, conference proceedings (conference presentations, proceedings and conference proceedings article), handbooks (guidelines and manuals), papers (such as journal articles, contributions to volumes).

Publication type (incl. Deliverables)	node name	publication number (per node)	publication number (H2IOSC)
Deliverable	E-RIHS.it	3	
Deliverable			11
Article (newspaper)	CLARIN-IT	1	
Book of abstract	E-RIHS.it	3	
Book chapter	E-RIHS.it	1	
Conference proceedings	CLARIN-IT	3	
Conference proceedings	DARIAH-IT	2	
Conference proceedings	E-RIHS.it	44	
Conference proceedings	OPERAS-IT	1	
Course	CLARIN-IT	2	
Handbook	CLARIN-IT	2	
Handbook			2
Paper	CLARIN-IT	5	
Paper	DARIAH-IT	5	
Paper	E-RIHS.it	51	
Paper	OPERAS-IT	1	
Paper			2
Poster	CLARIN-IT	4	
Poster	DARIAH-IT	3	
Poster	E-RIHS.it	13	
Poster	OPERAS-IT	1	
Poster			2
Technical report	CLARIN-IT	1	
Technical report	DARIAH-IT	1	
Tool	E-RIHS.it	1	

KPI Extent of assets provided to users by each RI node

Indicator	Extent of resources provided to users by each RI node
Definition(s)	<p>This KPI captures the extent and typology of the research-enabling resources made available by each RI node.</p> <p>For this KPI assets are defined as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data centers • Platforms • Services, which are categorized into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Digital services (including pilot implementations), ○ Technical services (provided by DCs), ○ Training services
Rationale	<p>This KPI reflects how actively the project contributes to the research ecosystem by providing usable scientific assets and services. The indicator provides insight into the operational capacity and service offering of each RI node.</p>
Assumptions	<p>It is assumed that all RI nodes are able to consistently report their available resources using shared classification criteria</p>
Data/information needs and resources	<p>Structured inventories detailing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of operational data centers • number of digital platforms in use • number of services made available, grouped into digital services (including pilots), technical services, and training services.
How is the KPI calculation carried out	<p>The KPI is calculated by summing the number of resources offered by each node, broken down by category.</p>
Who is providing this information	<p>Provided by RIs</p>
Sources	<p>Project documentation and inventories</p>
Unit of measure	<p>Number</p>

The measured KPI values are reported below.

The data investigated concerns the number of datacenters and platforms of individual nodes and the number of digital services (developed under WP6 and WP7) provided by the nodes. Since technical and training services are offered by the entire project team, they were counted as services of the cluster as a whole.

Resource type (DC, Platforms, Services)	node name	resource number (per node)	resource number (H2IOSC)
Technical Services			8
Training Services			2
Digital services	E-RIHS.it	21	
Digital services	CLARIN-IT	17	
Digital services	DARIAH-IT	11	
Digital services	OPERAS-IT	5	
DC	CLARIN-IT	1	
DC	DARIAH-IT	4	
DC	E-RIHS.it	3	
Platforms	CLARIN-IT	8	
Platforms	DARIAH-IT	4	
Platforms	E-RIHS.it	13	
Platforms	OPERAS-IT	3	

Data Collection and Analysis

The Infrastructure Node Performance Dashboard exploits data from project reports, financial records, project milestones, and deliverables. This dashboard is specifically designed to monitor the activities, outcomes, and challenges of each RI node within the project. It allows for an evaluation of each node's ability to meet project timelines, deliver high-quality outputs, and manage allocated resources efficiently. In doing so, the dashboard supports transparent governance, informed decision-making, and continuous alignment with project objectives and regulatory guidelines. In alignment with the development agendas of the participating RIs, and as outlined in § Section 2.2 "Data Collection and Analysis Report", the data collection process is integrated directly into ongoing activities and workflows.

Data sources:

- Deliverables and project reports,
- financial records,
- project milestones (including Intermediate Objectives in our case)
- data tracking systems implemented within each RI node.

3.1.2 Policy and Guideline Compliance Dashboard

This dashboard is intended to ensure that the project operates in compliance with the relevant regulations and legal frameworks. The monitoring also includes the publication of models,

standards, and guidelines, ensuring their communication and accessibility to all project participants.

The Policy and Guideline Compliance Dashboard is a tool to ensure adherence to policies and guidelines set forth by regulatory bodies and project directives. It serves as a centralized platform that enables stakeholders to monitor and assess the compliance efforts of the project, specifically focusing on policy and guideline implementation.

This dashboard consolidates information from various sources, including legal requirements, project directives, and internal policies, to provide a comprehensive overview of the project's compliance status. It utilizes visual representations to present the compliance data in a clear and intuitive manner.

Through the Policy and Guideline Compliance Dashboard, stakeholders can track the implementation of policies and guidelines across different aspects of the project. It provides insights into compliance with requirements related to deliverables submission, as well as other internal policies.

Furthermore, the Policy and Guideline Compliance Dashboard enables stakeholders to monitor the publication of relevant templates, standards and guidelines. It ensures that internal policies and project-specific guidelines are communicated effectively and made available to all relevant stakeholders. By tracking the dissemination of these documents, stakeholders can ensure that project participants are aware of their obligations and responsibilities.

The dashboard serves as a proactive tool for identifying areas of non-compliance or potential risks. It enables stakeholders to identify gaps in policy implementation, identify patterns of non-compliance, and take corrective actions to mitigate risks. By providing real-time insights into compliance efforts, the dashboard facilitates timely interventions and ensures that the project operates within legal and regulatory frameworks.

Overall, the Policy and Guideline Compliance Dashboard plays a crucial role in promoting transparency, accountability, and adherence to policies and guidelines within the H2IOSC project. It provides stakeholders with a comprehensive overview of compliance efforts, facilitates data-driven decision-making, and enables proactive risk management. Through this dashboard, the project can uphold the highest standards of integrity, legal compliance, and regulatory alignment, thereby ensuring the successful and ethical implementation of the project's objectives (i.e.: Shared Goals).

Key Performance Indicators:

KPI Number of policies and guidelines

Indicator	Number of policies and guidelines
Definition(s)	This KPI measures the extent to which relevant governance policies and guidelines, both pre-existing within the individual RIs and

	newly developed or adapted within the project, have been identified and mapped
Rationale	Tracking both existing and project-specific policy implementation ensures visibility into the governance maturity and harmonization of practices within the Federation.
Assumptions	RIs maintain records of policy and guidelines implementation; policy and guidelines making activities are mapped and documented within the project
Data/information needs and resources	Lists of existing RI policies relevant to the project; documentation of policies created or adapted within the project framework
How is the KPI calculation carried out	The KPI is calculated as the sum of policies already in place at each RI and relevant to the project (mapped and counted), and policies developed or tailored within the project and formally adopted by one or more RIs.
Who is providing this information	Provided by RIs
Sources	Project deliverables
Unit of measure	Number

The measured KPI values are reported below.

The compilation of the Number of Policies and Guidelines KPI table is mainly based on the work carried out within WP3 and WP6, which collected and organized information related to governance policies, service standards, and procedural guidelines adopted across the H2IOSC federation. In particular, for WP6, a primary source is the deliverable D6.2 “H2IOSC Services and Protocols”, which details the framework for service management, access procedures, and interoperability protocols. For WP3, the primary source was the deliverable D3.1 “Guidelines for Data, Services, Software Platform Policy Implementation”, which provided the foundational mapping of policies concerning data management, FAIR principles, and service alignment. The table therefore consolidates information derived from these two work packages, identifying for each RI the relevant policies and guidelines implemented or adapted within the project framework.

Policy type	node name	Policy number (per node)	Policy number (H2IOSC)
Service Manifests			1
Refactoring			1
Submission process	CLARIN-IT	1	
Data management	CLARIN-IT	1	

Long term preservation	CLARIN-IT	1	
Access and authentication	CLARIN-IT	1	
Data ingestion and management	DARIAH-IT	1	
Data transformation	DARIAH-IT	1	
Data exposition	DARIAH-IT	1	
Data visualisation	DARIAH-IT	1	
Data production and storage	E-RIHS.it	1	
Data curation	E-RIHS.it	1	
Processing	E-RIHS.it	1	
Publishing	E-RIHS.it	1	
Practical case	OPERAS-IT	1	

KPI Timeline compliance for documentation submission

Indicator	Timeline compliance for documentation submission
Definition(s)	This KPI monitors the adherence to planned delivery dates for technical reports to be submitted on GEA, including Intermediate Objectives (IOs) and deliverables. Other mandatory documents may be considered if their delivery is functional for IO and deliverables.
Rationale	Monitoring submission timeliness supports the coordination across the project. It also supports project management by highlighting possible delays that may affect interdependent activities or final deliverables.
Assumptions	Submission dates are clearly defined for all deliverables and outputs
Data/information needs and resources	Submission records indicating actual delivery dates for each document; internal monitoring reports or progress logs from WPs and RI nodes.
How is the KPI calculation carried out	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the number of documents (IOs and deliverables) due within the reporting period.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Count how many were submitted by the defined deadline (after the project extension). Calculate the percentage of on-time submission
Who is providing this information	Provided by RIs and GEA
Sources	Deliverables, logs by coordination team
Unit of measure	Percentage

The measured KPI values and some concluding comments are reported below.

TYPE	PERCENTAGE (%)
Technical reports	47
Deliverables	27
IO - <i>Civil Infrastructures</i>	0
IO - <i>Public call for applications for the competitive selection procedure for Temporary personnel</i>	62
IO - <i>Open Access, Transnational Access, FAIR principle implementation</i>	0
IO - <i>Public tender for scientific instrumentation and technological equipment acquisition</i>	0
IO – <i>Training/Phd</i>	0
IO - <i>Training and engagement Plan Developed</i>	0

Regarding **Technical Reports**, it should be noted that the percentage was calculated based on 17 technical reports submitted as of the date of this document. The first four reports were submitted in the following bimesters pending the resolution of some bugs in the GEA ministerial platform. The last four reports were submitted in the bimester following the one scheduled, pending receipt of all documentation relating to the DNSH forms associated with the relevant two-month period's acquisitions. The remaining eight were submitted by the scheduled deadline.

Regarding **Deliverables**, please note that the percentage was calculated based on 30 deliverables submitted as of the date of this document, of which 8 were submitted by the scheduled deadline. The delay for the other deliverables was primarily due to the fact that for most WPs, the expected staff was recruited later than expected, given the timeframes associated with selection procedures and some unsuccessful selections. This resulted in a delay of several months in the execution of activities and the subsequent preparation of the deliverables related to those activities. Furthermore, the project was extended by 6 months from the originally planned 30, which resulted in a different rescheduling of the deadlines for intermediate deliverables. In any case, at the end of October 2025, only the deliverables scheduled for the end of the project remain to be submitted, therefore the delay was made up without affecting the regular progress of the project.

Regarding the **intermediate objective "civil infrastructures"** it should be noted that the indicator used to verify its achievement is "N. of Civil Infrastructures related Public tenders published." Of a total of 16 tenders, most were published in bimester 7. The delay compared to the expected bimester 1 was due both to the delay in staff recruitment, as previously mentioned, and to the complexity of these tenders and the timing of their publication. In any case, by bimester 15, the objective was fully achieved.

Regarding the **intermediate objective "Public call for applications for the competitive selection procedure for Temporary personnel "** it should be noted that the indicator used to verify its achievement is "N. of Public calls for applications for the competitive selection procedure for Temporary personnel published." 62% of the 81 positions were published in the expected bimester 2, the remaining ones fully completed few months later (bimester 4) due to the number of the procedures and the concerned timeframe.

Regarding the **intermediate objective "Open Access, Transnational Access, FAIR principle implementation"** it should be noted that the indicator used to verify its achievement is "N. of Open Access, Transnational Access, FAIR principle implementation Public tenders awarded." Of a total of 42 tenders, most were awarded in bimester 7. The delay compared to the expected bimester 2 was due both to the delay in staff recruitment, as previously mentioned, and to the complexity of these tenders and the timing of their completion. In any case, by bimester 15, the objective was fully achieved.

Regarding the **intermediate objective "Public tender for scientific instrumentation and technological equipment acquisition"** it should be noted that the indicator used to verify its achievement is "N. of Public tenders (above-threshold procedures) for scientific instrumentation and technological equipment acquisition published". The objective was fully achieved in bimester 7. The delay compared to the expected bimester 3 was due to the same reason reported for the above-mentioned IOs.

Regarding the **intermediate objective "Training – PhD "** it should be noted that the indicator used to verify its achievement for training is "N. of Training activities related Public tenders awarded" and for Phd is "N. of PhDs activated." Of a total of 34 training tenders, most were awarded in bimester 7. The delay compared to the expected bimester 3 was due both to the delay in staff recruitment, as previously mentioned and to the timing of the procedures completion. In any case, by bimester 13, the objective was fully achieved for training activities. Of a total of 11 Phds, most were activated in bimester 7. The delay compared to the expected bimester 3 was due to the interactions with Universities which took more time than expected. In any case, by bimester 8, all Phds were activated.

Regarding the **intermediate objective "Training and engagement Plan Developed "** it should be noted that the indicator used to verify its achievement is "Training and engagement plan delivered". The Objective was achieved in bimester 6 instead of 5.

KPI Technological maturity monitoring

Indicator	Technological maturity monitoring
Definition(s)	This KPI measures the technological maturity of the services and pilots developed or adopted by each RI, using the TRL scale (from TRL 1: basic principles observed, to TRL 9: actual system proven in operational environment). The average TRL score per

	node reflects the overall readiness of services to be used reliably by the research community.
Rationale	This KPI provides insight into the project's technical progress.
Assumptions	TRL values are assigned using a standardized and consistent methodology; TRLs reflect realistic development stages at given milestones.
Data/information needs and resources	TRL assessments per service and per milestone; technical documentation
How is the KPI calculation carried out	extracting the detected TRL for each service
Who is providing this information	RI service coordinators and technical leads
Sources	Deliverables, TRL tracking logs
Unit of measure	Average TRL score (numeric, 1 to 9)

The measured KPI values are reported below.

The compilation of the Technological Maturity Monitoring KPI table is primarily based on the work carried out by WP3 on the assessment of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of services and pilots developed within H2IOSC. Specifically, the table draws directly from the dataset produced by WP3, which systematically tracks the evolution of technological maturity across the federation. From this reference table, we extracted three key fields: Research Infrastructure, Service, and TRL value corresponding to the most up-to-date TRL value, as of 31 October 2025, recorded in the WP3 dataset.

Service	Node Name	Final TRL detected at 31/10/2025
[E-RIHS] GRAVIFIX tool	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] 3D ANNOTATION tool	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] SimilarityLib	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] AI/ML solutions for Multimodal Datasets	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] Multimodal datasets visualization tool	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] HyMolab	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] ATON (WebXR services for HS)	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] Kapto	E-RIHS.it	8

[E-RIHS] SENNSE – Spatial Heritage Science Data Management - WSN Editor	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] Digital Fabrication Laboratory Virtual Access	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] Remotization for Digital Twins	E-RIHS.it	8
[E-RIHS] STONEVERSE	E-RIHS.it	8
[DARIAH] TIGRO - Tesoro Italiano delle Origini, gestore ricerche	DARIAH-IT	8
[DARIAH] EVT - Edition Visualization Technology	DARIAH-IT	8
[DARIAH] RAISE - Restore dAta Integration Suite	DARIAH-IT	8
[DARIAH] MFE - MetaFAIR Ecosystem	DARIAH-IT	8
[OPERAS] Remote Open Access to content-based services and resources. A pluggable distribution system that will ensure the remote use of the resources, services and hubs implemented by OPERAS within the H2IOSC project and, more generally, their remote, non real-time and possibly disconnected use 6.10	OPERAS-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] LexO ItAnt	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] CASH ItAnt	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] SKOSMOS Vocabulary Service	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] Triple Store (GraphDB)	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - EpiLexO ItAnt	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] Stanza NLP Chain	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - Stanza NLP Chain for ParlaMint Data	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] ILC PI - EpiLexO Editor	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] UDPipe	CLARIN-IT	9
[CLARIN-IT] Named Entity Recognition (NameTag)	CLARIN-IT	9
[CLARIN-IT] Federated Content Search (FCS)	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] TEI Publisher + eXist-db	CLARIN-IT	8
[CLARIN-IT] eScriptorium	CLARIN-IT	8

PILOT RATIO - FAST (Fairness ASessment Tool)	OPERAS-IT	8
PILOT RATIO - CONNECT (CollectiONs maiNtanencE and produCTion)	OPERAS-IT	8
PILOT NEST - New Science in Transition	OPERAS-IT	8
PILOT OSTGL - Open Scholarly and Technical Grey Literature Platform	OPERAS-IT	8
PILOT Interlumo	E-RIHS.it	8
PILOT Illuminated manuscript HUB	E-RIHS.it	8
PILOT HeriVerse-Heritage Science Metaverse	E-RIHS.it	8
PILOT SENNSE - Spatial hEritage scieNce oNline Sensor Environment	E-RIHS.it	8
PILOT Open Digital Archaeology Hub	E-RIHS.it	9
PILOT Open Digital Epigraphy Hub	E-RIHS.it	9
PILOT Scientific Digital Hub for Painting Collections	E-RIHS.it	8
PILOT Prototyping platform for Virtual / Physical Exhibitions	E-RIHS.it	7
PILOT Scientific digital hub for metal artworks	E-RIHS.it	8
PILOT Digital Philology Hub	DARIAH-IT	8
PILOT Digital Heritage and Memory Hub	DARIAH-IT	8
PILOT Archivio Vi.Vo. (Oral Data Platform)	CLARIN-IT	8
PILOT Linguistic Linked Open Data (LLOD) Platform	CLARIN-IT	8
PILOT TaskLet (Framework for Psycholinguistic Tasks)	CLARIN-IT	8

Data Collection and Analysis:

The data for these KPIs can be gathered through project deliverables, and technical reports. The analysis should focus on identifying trends, patterns, and potential risk areas.

The findings should be used to continuously improve the compliance process and minimize risks.

3.1.3 Partnership and Networking Performance Dashboard

The Partnership and Networking Performance Dashboard is a dynamic tool to monitor and assess the effectiveness of partnerships and networking activities. It serves as a centralized platform that enables stakeholders to evaluate the collaborative efforts and synergies established with relevant actors in the field of research and innovation.

This dashboard consolidates data from various sources, including possible agreements, joint initiatives, and networking events. It provides stakeholders with a comprehensive view of the project's partnership landscape and the impact of these collaborations on the project's outcomes.

Through the Partnership and Networking Performance Dashboard, stakeholders can assess the quality and quantity of partnerships established within the project. It provides insights into the diversity of stakeholders involved, and the alignment of partners' expertise and resources with the project's objectives. Stakeholders can evaluate the success of partnerships in terms of joint research endeavors, knowledge exchange, technology transfer, and possible industry engagement.

The dashboard facilitates the monitoring of networking activities carried out by the project, such as workshops, conferences, and seminars. It provides information on the number of events organized, participant engagement, and the dissemination of project results. By tracking these networking activities, stakeholders can gauge the level of visibility, reach, and impact achieved through these initiatives.

Furthermore, the Partnership and Networking Performance Dashboard enables stakeholders to assess the outcomes and impact of collaborations. It tracks (for example) metrics such as publications, joint projects resulting from partnerships established within the project. This helps stakeholders understand the tangible benefits and contributions of partnerships to the project's overall objectives and outcomes.

The dashboard also serves as a tool for identifying potential areas of partnership opportunities. It can highlight gaps in collaborations or sectors that require more engagement. By identifying these areas, stakeholders can take proactive measures to foster new partnerships, strengthen existing relationships, and leverage the expertise and resources of relevant actors.

Overall, the Partnership and Networking Performance Dashboard plays a crucial role in facilitating effective collaboration and maximizing the impact of the H2IOSC project. It provides stakeholders with a comprehensive overview of partnership efforts, enables data-driven decision-making, and promotes evidence-based interventions to enhance networking activities. Through this dashboard, the project can build robust partnerships, foster knowledge exchange, and drive innovation within the field of humanities and cultural heritage research.

Key Performance Indicators:

KPI - Number of networking events organized

Indicator	Number of networking events organised
Definition(s)	The KPI refers to the count of formal or informal events specifically designed to bring together stakeholders, professionals or participants with the primary goal of facilitating connections, partnerships, knowledge sharing or collaboration.
Rationale	Networking events foster partnerships and inter-organizational cooperation; they can lead to new business opportunities or strategic alliances; they are useful for management to track stakeholder engagement activities; they reflect how actively the project promotes interaction and growth, technology transfer.
Assumptions	Events are organized intentionally for networking; events have a clear objective related to stakeholder interaction, professional relationship building, or collaboration; only distinct events are counted.
Data/information needs and resources	Event Name/Title; Date(s) of the Event; Event Objective; Type of Event; Location or Mode (physical/virtual).
How is the KPI calculation carried out	Sum of events of this type.
Who is providing this information	Provided by the project governance or CNR
Sources	Webpage
Unit of measure	Number

The measured KPI values are reported below.

The analyzed data concerns the number of events from the start of the project until 31 October 2025, which saw the participation of individual nodes and the H2IOSC cluster.

Event type	node name	event number (per node)	Event number (H2IOSC)
General Meeting			1
Festival			1
Workshop			2
Conference	CLARIN-IT	13	
Conference	DARIAH-IT	7	
Conference	E-RIHS.it	41	
Conference	OPERAS-IT	3	
Conference and workshop	DARIAH-IT	1	
Conference and workshop	OPERAS-IT	1	
Event	CLARIN-IT	1	
Event	DARIAH-IT	5	
Event	E-RIHS.it	3	
Event and workshop	E-RIHS.it	1	
Exhibition	E-RIHS.it	1	
Expo	E-RIHS.it	4	
Meeting	CLARIN-IT	1	
Round table	E-RIHS.it	3	
Seminar including a webinar	CLARIN-IT	8	
Study day	CLARIN-IT	2	
Study day	E-RIHS.it	1	
Symposium	E-RIHS.it	2	
Talk	CLARIN-IT	4	
Training School (including a Summer School)	CLARIN-IT	3	
Tutorial	CLARIN-IT	1	
Workshop	CLARIN-IT	2	
Workshop	DARIAH-IT	1	

Workshop	E-RIHS-IT	10	
Workshop	OPERAS-IT	1	

KPI - Number of publications on the same thematic area

Indicator	Number of publications on the same thematic area
Definition(s)	It refers to the count of publications that fall within a defined thematic or disciplinary area (Delibera CNR n. 126/2024).
Rationale	Evaluate the research productivity in a specific field. Assess the specialization or focus of a research group. Track trends in research output in specific subject areas.
Assumptions	Publications reflect research activity and output. Thematic areas are defined consistently using recognized classification systems (following Delibera CNR n. 126/2024). Databases and sources provide accurate and comprehensive coverage of relevant publications. Authorship and attribution are correctly assigned.
Data/information needs and resources	A reliable bibliographic database (zenodo)
How is the KPI calculation carried out	Sum of publications per area
Who is providing this information	Provided by the project governance or CNR
Sources	Database
Unit of measure	Number

The measured KPI values are reported below.

The data investigated concern the number of publications, per thematic area (Delibera CNR n. 126/2024), carried out from the beginning of the project until 31 October 2025, prepared by the individual nodes and the H2IOSC cluster,

Thematic area of the publication	node name	publication number (per node)	publication number (H2IOSC)
PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	CLARIN-IT	1	
PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques	E-RIHS.it	1	
PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, natural language processing	DARIAH-IT	2	
PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, natural language processing	OPERAS-IT	1	
PE6_8 Computer graphics, computer vision, multimedia, computer games	E-RIHS.it	1	
PE6_9 Human computer interaction and interface, visualisation	E-RIHS.it	6	
PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	CLARIN-IT	1	
PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	E-RIHS.it	5	
PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	OPERAS-IT	1	
PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video)	DARIAH-IT	2	
PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and	E-RIHS.it	1	

applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video)			
SH4_9 - Theoretical linguistics; computational linguistics	E-RIHS.it	1	
SH5_4 Philology; text and image studies	E-RIHS.it	2	
SH5_11 - Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	CLARIN-IT	7	
SH5_11 - Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	E-RIHS.it	29	
SH5_11 - Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere	DARIAH-IT	3	
SH5_11 - Digital humanities; computational and digital approaches in the cultural sphere			2
SH6_5 Archaeological science, bioarchaeology, environmental archaeology, geoarchaeology	E-RIHS.it	1	
SH6_6 Digital, computational, virtual and geospatial archaeologies	E-RIHS.it	5	
SH8_3 Cultural studies and theory, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage, architectural heritage	E-RIHS.it	3	
SH8_9 Digital approaches to anthropology, cultural studies and art	E-RIHS.it	7	
SH8_-Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage	CLARIN-IT	8	
SH8_-Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage	DARIAH-IT	5	
SH8_-Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage	E-RIHS.it	56	
SH8_-Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage	OPERAS-IT	6	
SH8_-Science and Technologies for Cultural Heritage			8

KPI - Areas of partnership opportunities

Indicator	Areas of partnership opportunities
Definition(s)	Areas of partnership opportunities are potential activities where strategic collaboration between partners can lead to synergies, improved efficiency, access to innovation, or shared resources.
Rationale	Partnerships are formed to combine complementary capabilities, share risks and costs, accelerate growth or innovation, enhance credibility or legitimacy, improve operational efficiency through shared infrastructure or knowledge.
Assumptions	The partners have compatible goals or interests; there is mutual trust and willingness to collaborate; each partner brings value to the table (skills, assets, etc.).
Data/information needs and resources	To identify and evaluate areas of partnership opportunities, the following data are typically needed: strategic objectives and priorities, core competencies and capabilities, resource availability, operational strengths and weaknesses, user needs.
How is the KPI calculation carried out	SWOT Matching Matrix, Gap Analysis, interviews.
Who is providing this information	Provided by the project governance or CNR
Sources	Networking events, joint initiatives, survey
Unit of measure	Descriptive field

Below is a description of some of the partnership areas identified.

H2IOSC, like other NRRP-funded projects, initiated discussions to seek potential partners for collaboration based on shared goals and mutual interest in their capabilities and expertise. Noteworthy is the initiation of discussions for a possible collaboration between H2IOSC, ITSERR (<https://www.itserr.it/>), CHANGES (<https://www.fondazionechanges.org/pnrr/>), and SAMOTHRACE (<https://samothrace.eu/>). H2IOSC is the key infrastructure for Open Science in the

humanities and heritage sciences, enabling advanced data management, supercomputing, and digital knowledge representation. In synergy, the other projects cited contribute specific resources and expertise, strengthening the scientific and cultural impact of the entire ecosystem. The collaboration would develop its technical and scientific activities along four main lines:

1. OPEN CH: cross-sector collaborative environments based on H2IOSC with knowledge graphs for historical-artistic and archaeological interpretation, integrating multidimensional open-linked data.
2. RESILIENT CH: Digital twin for monitoring and preventing risks to material heritage, with sensors and predictive analytics.
3. ACCESSIBLE CH: Technologies for heritage accessibility and inclusiveness, through interfaces, immersive experiences, and haptic devices.
4. TEXTUAL & INTANGIBLE CH: Digital environments for text and documentation sciences, with tools for handwriting recognition, corpora management, and computer-assisted editing.

Another noteworthy collaboration, which led to the submission of a joint project under PON call no. 310 of March 18, 2025, is between H2IOSC and FOSSR (<https://www.fossr.eu/>), an alliance of clusters of Advanced Research Infrastructures in the Social, Human, and Heritage Sciences for the Sustainable Digital Development of Southern Italy. The project's primary objective is to promote the creation and strengthening of thematic and multidisciplinary networks between research infrastructures, universities, associations, businesses, and public administrations. Common platforms for data management and sharing would be developed in accordance with FAIR principles, with shared standards for interoperability, common access protocols, federated services for resource use, and coordinated internationalization, dissemination, and training efforts. The project includes the creation of a "Digital Knowledge Academy" for training and the transfer of digital knowledge and technologies "from science to business" and two "Data Factories" to support businesses (the "Innovation Data Factory") and companies operating in the culture, cultural heritage, and tourism sectors (the "Cultural Data Factory") in alignment with public decision-makers.

However, it is planned to intensify this search for potential new public and private partners, to also ensure the medium-long term sustainability of the H2IOSC federation as reported in deliverable 1.4

KPI - Sectors that require more engagement.

Indicator	Sectors that require more engagement.
-----------	---------------------------------------

Definition(s)	Sectors that require more engagement are areas of activity where current involvement by stakeholders is not sufficient to meet needs, solve problems, or capitalize on opportunities.
Rationale	Addressing Gaps: to identify and address areas with unmet needs or underperformance.
Assumptions	Resource Constraints Exist: not all sectors can receive equal attention or funding. Current Engagement is uneven: some sectors naturally attract more interest while others lag behind.
Data/information needs and resources	Performance Indicators: output, productivity, coverage, efficiency, impact. Stakeholder Analysis: number and diversity of actors involved. Government policy or regulatory support. Demand-Supply Analysis: unmet needs or service gaps, community demand not being met.
How is the KPI calculation carried out	Stakeholder Involvement: number of active actors; Outcome Metrics: achievement vs. targets, survey data.
Who is providing this information	Provided by the project governance or CNR
Sources	Networking events, joint initiatives, survey
Unit of measure	Descriptive field

Below is a description of sectors that require more engagement.

One of the areas where greater commitment is needed within the cluster concerns the involvement of businesses, both as potential partners in the co-development of innovative solutions and as potential users of the services provided. This emerged from a survey conducted with H2IOSC service providers (the type of user and partner was asked) and during several events open to this type of audience. The first event took place on 22-23/01/2025, organized by the Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, Cultural Heritage of the National Research Council (CNR) and entitled “ESFRI research infrastructures in the social and humanities sciences and cultural heritage: engines of innovation for research in Italy and Europe”, whose agenda can be found at the following link: <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/presentation-of-esfri-research-infrastructures-in-social->

[sciences-humanities-and-cultural-heritage-engines-of-innovation-for-research-in-italy-and-europe/](#), at the CNR (Italy). Another opportunity for discussion with the entrepreneurial side took place on June 17, 2025, during the Webinar organized by Invitalia-CNR, entitled "The opportunities of the CNR SSHOpenCloud.IT project for startups," to present the two clusters participating in the aforementioned PON call no. 310/2025. The agenda for the webinar can be found at the following link: <https://events.teams.microsoft.com/event/6561d6da-bfdc-4bcb-9bd4-76fb081a33b3@afd0a75c-8671-4cce-9061-2ca0d92e422f>. Another important event was organized by the H2IOSC cluster in Naples on July 8 and 9, 2025, to present its services to the academic and business world (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/h2iosc-meets-public-and-private-sectors-in-naples/>). Following these events, questionnaires were sent to participants to assess their level of knowledge and interest in Research Infrastructures and their services to facilitate comparison and matching between supply and demand for innovation. This highlighted the need to continue investing in similar events to encourage increasingly active entrepreneurial participation.

Another important point to focus on is the diversification of services offered by the H2IOSC cluster, which is requested in providing an increasingly customized offering tailored to user needs and with increasingly targeted technical assistance. This emerged from the evaluation questionnaires completed by users participating in the TNA/NA calls organized by the Cluster, described in detail in Deliverable 1.2. Further details are available at the following link (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/tna-na-calls/>).

This activity, which should also be intensified, is part of the sustainability perspective described in Deliverable 1.4.

3.1.4 Facilities, tools and Services Management Dashboard

The Facilities, Tools and Services Management Dashboard is intended as a central monitoring and coordination tool for tracking the operational capacity and service provision capabilities of the H2IOSC research infrastructure nodes. The dashboard relies on qualitative descriptors due to the limited availability of consolidated data, in future updates the dashboard can include structured and quantitative KPIs.

Descriptor A – Use of Facilities and Service Offer

This descriptor captures the current state of activation, accessibility, and functional readiness of research facilities and the availability of research services provided by H2IOSC nodes.

Qualitative inputs include:

- Type and function of infrastructure (labs, data centers, technical spaces);
- Access modes (remote/on-site);
- Known infrastructural bottlenecks or service delivery issues;

- Availability and visibility of services offered (e.g., data processing, technical support);
- Booking/request mechanisms where available.

Descriptor B – Tools, Equipment and Operational Supplies

This descriptor reports on the status and operational continuity of research tools, technical equipment, and core consumables.

Qualitative inputs include:

- Equipment distribution across RIs and scientific domains;
- Maintenance or calibration cycles, usage constraints;
- Obsolescence issues and replacement planning;
- Availability and management of consumables, reagents, ICT resources;
- Procurement, logistics, and potential supply bottlenecks.

In the current implementation of the Facilities, Tools, and Services Management Dashboard, qualitative descriptors have been adopted. This approach ensures that the dashboard remains operationally relevant and informative, while also laying the groundwork for the progressive integration of quantitative KPIs in future updates. Expected evidence includes usage narratives, access policies, internal service catalogues, and improvement plans.

3.1.5 Strategic Development and Collaboration Dashboard

The Strategic Development and Collaboration Dashboard is a tool to facilitate the planning, coordination, and monitoring of strategic initiatives and collaborative efforts. It serves to align project activities (e.g.: Key Activities) with strategic objectives (e.g.: Shared Goals), foster collaboration among project participants, and track the progress of strategic initiatives.

This dashboard consolidates data from various sources, including (for example) strategic plans, project roadmaps and progress reports. It provides stakeholders with a holistic view of the project's strategic directions, objectives, and milestones.

Through the Strategic Development and Collaboration Dashboard, stakeholders can effectively monitor the alignment of project activities with strategic goals, ensuring that resources and efforts are directed towards achieving the desired outcomes.

Stakeholders can identify opportunities for partnerships, leverage expertise, and share best practices, enhancing the overall impact of the project.

Through this dashboard, the project can ensure the effective implementation of strategic objectives, maximize collaboration and knowledge exchange, and achieve transformative impact in the field of humanities and cultural heritage research, having an in-depth and up-to-date knowledge of the costs associated with operating the cluster, the possible sources of funding, the types of services and activities of interest and a better allocation of available resources.

Key Performance Indicators:

KPI – Value proposition of H2IOSC

Indicator	Value proposition of H2IOSC
Definition(s)	The KPI describes the unique value that H2IOSC delivers. It answers: What problem is being solved? Who will benefit and how?
Rationale	The rationale provides the justification for undertaking the project: What are the strategic goals? What is the impact of not doing the cluster? What competitive advantage or operational efficiency will be gained?
Assumptions	The target user needs or wants the solution. The costs are predictable and controllable. Stakeholders will support H2IOSC also in the future. Technology or resources will be available and sufficient.
Data/information needs and resources	To develop and support the value proposition, the following data is needed: Market data (demand, competition), Financial data (cost estimates, revenues), Stakeholder feedback (needs, expectations, pain points), Risk assessments (potential roadblocks, mitigation). Resources: mainly, technological and human resources.
How is the KPI calculation carried out	Stakeholder and service providers interviews; User journey mapping; Competitive analysis.
Who is providing this information	Stakeholder, project community, service providers, users, suppliers.
Sources	Survey
Unit of measure	Descriptive field

Below is a description of the H2IOSC Value proposition investigated.

The value proposition was explored within the cluster from various perspectives. First, it was surveyed of the project community at large, as stakeholders but also users of the infrastructure facilities participating in H2IOSC and their services (recurring responses: “More opportunities for collaboration between researchers and infrastructure” and “Simplified and shared access to research resources and data”). It was then strategically explored with the coordinators of the four national infrastructure nodes (some responses: “Extended partnership”, “Developing attractive and innovative services/new technologies”). It was then analyzed through surveys with the scientific community using

the services (some responses: “Updating on available resources “, “Complete and useful metadata for research purposes “) and with users of the services included in the TNA/NA calls (recurring responses: “Enabled access to advanced and reliable digital tools/resources provided by research infrastructures” and “Improved the quality or efficiency of our research processes and data with the help of H2IOSC technologies and expertise”). For a detailed analysis of the results, please refer to deliverable 1.4, which specifically addresses this aspect. However, it is the intention of the cluster management to maintain focus on this aspect by repeating questionnaires so as not to lose touch with the stakeholders' strategic vision and the needs of scientific and non-scientific users.

KPI – Key services

Indicator	Key services
Definition(s)	Key services of H2IOSC are the essential activities and supports it provides to enable, enhance, or facilitate research.
Rationale	Enable external researchers and industry to use the infrastructure, often via open access or peer review.
Assumptions	Access must be equitable and transparent. H2IOSC can support external demand without disrupting internal research.
Data/information needs and resources	Category of services. Type of services free (standard services) and paid (value added services). Possible users, partners, competitors. Possible services request. Costs for equipment and dedicated staff. Possible fee for value added services.
How is the KPI calculation carried out	Service providers interviews; User/partner mapping; Competitive analysis.
Who is providing this information	Project community, service providers, users, suppliers. Industry.
Sources	Survey, benchmark analysis, network events.
Unit of measure	Descriptive field

Below is a description of H2IOSC Key Services.

The following are the macro categories of services of the H2IOSC cluster catalogue.

- **Technical services:** digital infrastructures essential for research and data management, including solutions for secure storage, high-performance computing, AI-powered content analysis, and advanced ICT services to support processing, sharing, and interoperability of data within virtual and collaborative research environments.
- **Data & Digital services:** software, tools, datasets, and pilot projects addressing the needs of those involved in the study, management, and valorization of cultural, linguistic, and historical heritage, including tools for remote monitoring, diagnostics, data extraction and analysis, and digital fabrication.
- **Research services:** access to platforms (physical, digital, etc.) for carrying out scientific experiments/use of cutting-edge tools and equipment to support scientific excellence.
- **Innovation services:** synergies of existing tools and new innovative research capabilities.
- **Training services:** free self-paced courses and platforms for sharing and downloading open-access training materials, tailored for people involved in the humanities, social sciences, and heritage science, to strengthen interdisciplinary skills and the use of Research Infrastructures.

With regard to the methods of access to H2IOSC services:

- **Open access resources:** access to these resources is free-of-charge.
- **Value-added resources:** for added-value resources and services (i.e.: services for scientific research and access to the technological infrastructure) a flexible model is used that considers different categories of users:
 1. **Users of the scientific network:** access, granted on the basis of scientific excellence and the potential impact of the proposed research project, involving a selection process, requires the payment of a contribution to cover the costs of providing the service.
 2. **Private users:** access is guaranteed by paying a fee required for the use of specific services or features that enrich the basic offer of the infrastructure, such as advanced features, specialized support or customized solutions that meet specific needs. The fees help to cover the costs of development, maintenance, support and provision of these services.

Further details on these services, their potential partners/users/competitors, and access policies are provided in deliverable 1.4.

It is important to note that the service categorization is the one identified in the project context. During the cluster's full operational phase, it may undergo changes both in the

type and number of services offered and in their possible combination, with a view to responding increasingly efficiently to interested parties' requests.

KPI – Cost analysis

Indicator	Cost analysis
Definition(s)	Cost analysis refers to the identification, quantification, and evaluation of all cost elements related to the lifecycle of the H2IOSC. It includes capital investments, operational expenses, personnel costs, R&D and indirect costs, with the aim to ensure efficient resource allocation and long-term sustainability.
Rationale	Budget planning and allocation: Helps funders and managers understand the true cost of the cluster. Sustainability assessment: Ensures the cluster can operate long-term without financial risk. Decision support: Informs strategic choices. Efficiency monitoring: Identifies cost drivers and potential savings. Funding applications: Required by governments and institutions for justifying investment.
Assumptions	Cost analyses usually rely on a few key assumptions: Useful life of infrastructures (e.g., 20 years). Utilization rates of the infrastructure (how intensively it's used). Technological stability (i.e., pace of obsolescence). Staffing models. Maintenance and replacement schedules for equipment.
Data/information needs and resources	Capital costs (investment done and to be done); Operating costs (Personnel, utilities, consumables, maintenance); Indirect costs.
How is the KPI calculation carried out	Data centers/platforms referents interviews, suppliers interviews.
Who is providing this information	Data centers/platforms referents, suppliers.
Sources	Survey

Unit of measure	Number
-----------------	--------

The values of the cost analysis are reported below.

Cost categories	Description	Value 2026-2035 (kEuro)
Investment costs	The amount was estimated considering the 5-year life cycle of the hardware (data center) equipment acquired with NRPP funds, in order to maintain the cluster's high-performance and cutting-edge capabilities. For the data centers, it was therefore estimated that the same level of investment would be sustained at the end of the 5 years. For the platforms acquired with NRPP funds, a diversified valuation was applied, taking into account their complexity and technical specificities.	15.682
Running costs	The amount was estimated considering the potential maintenance and consumables costs, as well as utilities, for the first five years and ten years of the data centers, taking into account that these data centers (may) also consist of equipment previously acquired with non-NRPP funds, but whose maintenance was necessarily considered, for technical and functional reasons, in conjunction with the equipment acquired with project funds. The amount also includes technical support costs for the platforms over the same period and, finally, the maintenance and consumables costs associated with the services listed in the catalogue.	27.396
R&D costs	costs for research and development activities that are planned to be outsourced to suppliers in order to ensure the efficiency and performance standards required of H2IOSC platforms and services. Research and development activities related to the data centers and most of the platforms used are carried out by cluster	2.902

	personnel, the cost of which is reported under "manpower costs" item.	
Manpower costs	The amount was estimated based on an analysis of the manpower requirements for the cluster's management and operations in the coming years. The analysis specifically considered the manpower required for the proper functioning of the data centers and platforms used for the purposes of the H2IOSC cluster, as well as for the proper provision of the services listed in the catalogue. It takes into account permanent staff already employed in the aforementioned activities and temporary staff who may be hired to upgrade certain services, based on the projects won.	23.890
Overheads	calculated as 7% of direct costs previous listed, to use the same percentage applied under the NRRP-funded project.	4.891

KPI – Revenues

Indicator	Revenues
Definition(s)	It refers to the income generated by the cluster from its operations, services, and other funding sources.
Rationale	Assess its financial sustainability. Inform policy decisions and funding strategies. Measure its economic impact and return on investment. Improve efficiency and planning for future development. Justify public funding by showing value generated.
Assumptions	Revenue includes public and private contributions, grants, and service fees. The cluster provides valuable outputs (data, technology, knowledge) that others are willing to pay for or support. Revenue generation does not necessarily imply profit motive.

Data/information needs and resources	Revenue from services or user fees, National/international grants, Institutional funding
How is the KPI calculation carried out	Sum of the relevant sources
Who is providing this information	Management of the project
Sources	Annual financial statements, project budget allocation
Unit of measure	Number

The values of the revenues and some concluding comments are reported below.

Revenue categories	Description	Value 2026-2035 (kEuro)
National Nodes Core budget	This is constituted by Ordinary government funding (FOE). To be understood as financing of the " <i>FOE a valenza internazionale</i> ", which is expected to be (partly) allocated for the reference period. This Core Budget serves the basic funding for H2IOSC operation, ensuring the continuous functioning of its Nodes. Indeed, H2IOSC is sustained through indirect funding mechanisms, with financial resources provided via the national nodes, rather than through direct centralised allocations.	3.400
EU research and national projects income	To be understood as an estimated value based on the projects financed in the last 5 years (2019-2024), taking into account the fact that the trend of projects won in the recent period is confirmed. European research and national grants will provide additional funding for the development of specific H2IOSC activities and/or services, and for future investments, both at the cluster level and at the Nodes level.	8.690
Service fee	Forecast based on expected requests for access to technical, training and digital added-value services for which the payment of a contribution or fee is expected, calculated taking into account the analysis of the	2.051

	demand for services and the trend of services already operational requested. The contributions and fees are requested to cover mainly the costs associated with making the same services available.	
Other revenues	In order to ensure full coverage of the costs associated with the correct operation of the national Nodes. Specifically, these funds include the FOE (Institutional Fund) to cover the cost of permanent staff and utilities costs, as well as a revenue forecast for public-private partnerships that are planned to be activated in the long term and for which networking activities have been initiated during the project's life cycle.	60.620

Further details on costs, revenues and financial sustainability are provided in deliverable 1.4.

It is important to take into account the assumptions made in the mentioned deliverable and the fact that the forecasts will necessarily have to be monitored and updated based on the progress of the cluster's activities, its services, and other contingent situations.

3.1.6 Performance Measurement and Assessment Dashboard

The Performance Measurement and Assessment Dashboard is a comprehensive tool designed to track and evaluate the progress, performance, and impact of the H2IOSC project. It serves as a centralized platform that provides real-time insights into various aspects of the project's implementation and outcomes. The dashboard incorporates key performance indicators (KPIs) and metrics aligned with the project's objectives, considering those defined by the project technical sheet, allowing stakeholders, including the Project decision-making structure, to monitor the project's performance against predetermined targets.

Through the Performance Measurement and Assessment Dashboard, stakeholders can assess the effectiveness and efficiency of the project's activities, identifying areas of success and areas that require improvement.

The Performance Measurement and Assessment Dashboard serves as a valuable decision-making tool, supporting stakeholders in making informed choices to ensure the project's success. It facilitates data-driven discussions, enables the identification of trends and patterns, and provides a basis for evidence-based interventions and adjustments to project implementation strategies.

Overall, the Performance Measurement and Assessment Dashboard acts as a practical resource, consolidating project knowledge and offering valuable support to stakeholders. It provides a comprehensive assessment of the project's implementation conditions, offering insights into its achievements, challenges, and areas for improvement. By leveraging the dashboard's functionalities, stakeholders can effectively monitor and evaluate the H2IOSC project's progress, facilitating the attainment of project objectives and maximizing its impact in the field of humanities and cultural heritage research and innovation.

With the aim to support monitoring and evaluation activities within the H2IOSC project, as described in sections 5 (Monitoring) and 6 (Reporting) of D1.1, we report in the following the relevant Key indicators found for both procedural and financial progress of the project.

KPI – Procedural progress of the project

Indicator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of days to fill in and sign checklist for <u>recruitment</u> (checklist 6) and for <u>procurement</u> (checklist 7); • Number of days to upload checklist 6 and 7 on OwnCloud signed by the Director.
Definition(s)	They assess through the implementation of self-monitoring reviews for recruitment and procurement procedures have been completed at a given point in time, compared to a baseline or timeline.
Rationale	Ensure timely implementation of project activities. Monitor workflow, task completion, and administrative processes. Identify delays or deviations early for corrective action. Promote accountability among teams and stakeholders. Support resource planning and decision-making during project execution.
Assumptions	A clearly defined work plan or project schedule exists. Tasks and milestones are well-defined with assigned responsibilities. Delays and deviations can be quantified and investigated.
Data/information needs and resources	Project work plan and activity schedule, Milestone definitions and due dates. Records of task completions (checklists).

How is the KPI calculation carried out	Use of tracking tools for data entry and monitoring.
Who is providing this information	Management and administrative staff.
Sources	CNR Owncloud and Sharepoint Workbook
Unit of measure	Number

The values of the identified KPIs and some concluding comments are reported below.

Procedural indicators (Number of days)	BIM4 BIM5 BIM6	BIM7 BIM8 BIM9	BIM10 BIM11 BIM12	BIM13 BIM14 BIM15
Procedural indicators for <u>recruitment</u> : Number of days for fill out and signature of the checklist 6	38,88	61,66	62,93	-
Procedural indicators for <u>procurement</u> : Number of days for fill out and signature of the checklist 7	85,69	153,74	192,10	83,44
Procedural indicators: Number of days for fill out and signature of the checklist 6 and 7	BIM4 BIM5 BIM6	BIM7 BIM8 BIM9	BIM10 BIM11 BIM12	BIM13 BIM14 BIM15
Procedural indicators for <u>recruitment</u> : Number days to update checklist 6 in OwnCloud after Director's signature	2,92	2,11	0,00	-
Procedural indicators for <u>procurement</u> : Number days to update checklist 7 in OwnCloud after Director's signature	1,67	0,00	0,00	0,00

As described in section 6 (Reporting) of D1.1 and set out in the Procedural and Financial workflows, the checklists “Annex 6 for recruitment procedures” and “Annex 7 for procurement procedures” drafted by the Ministry, were shared by the H2IOSC Financial Manager with the UOs.

All the Institutes considered that the implementation of self-monitoring reviews for recruitment and procurement procedures through the checklists was a valid tool. The Institutes considered this process essential in order to ensure that the information and documentation required for all procedures carried out was consistent and complete. However, the implementation of self-assessment process required more time than expected,

particularly during the periods between BIM7 and BIM12 when the relevant part of procedures was carried out.

The use of the OwnCloud repository, described in section 5 (Monitoring) of D1.1, for uploading checklists 6 and 7 signed by the Directors was well valued and rapidly implemented by the Institutes, with an improvement leading to zero days between the Director's signature and the uploading to the repository as the reporting activities advanced.

KPI – Financial progress of the project

Indicator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of days to fill in and sign the declaration of the actual work performed by the recruited personnel (DSAN); • Number of days for payment of procurement invoices.
Definition(s)	They reflect the degree to which the project has utilized its allocated financial resources in relation to planned expenditure in compliance with the timelines set out in national legislation on payments for public bodies.
Rationale	To track whether spending aligns with project milestones and timelines. To help detect under- or over-spending, financial inefficiencies. To support decision-making related to risk management, or corrective actions.
Assumptions	Project activities are progressing as per the implementation schedule, so financial progress reflects physical progress.
Data/information needs and resources	Actual expenditure to date, Project budget documents, Financial reports (e.g., invoices, accounting statements)
How is the KPI calculation carried out	Use of tracking tools for data entry and monitoring.
Who is providing this information	Management and administrative staff.
Sources	Integrated System for the Accounting Management, CNR Owncloud and Sharepoint Workbook

Unit of measure	Number
-----------------	--------

The values of the identified KPIs and some concluding comments are reported below.

Financial indicators (Number of days)	BIM4 BIM5 BIM6	BIM7 BIM8 BIM9	BIM10 BIM11 BIM12	BIM13 BIM14 BIM15
Financial indicators for <u>recruitment</u> : Number of days for fill out and sign the DSAN (2 Days)	8,97	18,11	15,62	15,77
Financial indicators for <u>procurement</u> : Number of days to pay (30 Days)	18,83	29,84	39,96	28,21

As described in section 6 (Reporting) of D1.1, the Financial workflow is the basis for assessing KPIs related to the days required to fill in and sign the declaration of the actual work performed by the recruited personnel (DSAN) and to the compliance with the timelines set out by national legislation for public bodies when analysing the timeliness payment of procurement invoices.

As noted in the analysis of procedural indicators, in the period starting from BIM7, the timing was higher than in the previous period due to a increased number of recruitment and procurement procedures. Differently from procedural indicators, most of which were completed at BIM12, financial indicators show no decrease since financial reporting activities still involve all recruited personnel and the payment of invoices related to the progress of procurement. It should be noted that the indicators for invoice payment are lower than those required by national legislation although the change in the CNR's Integrated System for the Accountig Management has slightly increased the average payment times.

3.2 Description of actors involved and the expected impact on implementation conditions

The processes of design and implementation of the dashboards described in the previous points (see Sections 2.1 Approach and framework for assessing implementation conditions and 2.2 Data collection and analysis methods) involve various actors who play crucial roles in ensuring the success of these operations. These actors can be categorized into different groups based on their involvement and responsibilities:

Research Infrastructures Coordinators (RICs) and Work Package Leaders, WPLs: they play a central role in overseeing the implementation of the dashboards. They are responsible for defining the set of Key Activities needed to achieve the Shared Goals (and thus the Key Exploitable Results), identifying the key performance indicators (KPIs), and setting the overall

direction for the dashboards' development and implementation. They collaborate to ensure that the dashboards align with the project's goals and requirements.

Gruppo di Coordinamento Tecnico (GCT): The Gruppo di Coordinamento Tecnico is responsible for the technical aspects of implementing the dashboards. They work closely with RICs and WPLs to understand the data requirements, integrate data from various sources, and support the development of the necessary components and tools.

Project Management Board (PMB): among the primary beneficiaries of the dashboards, they rely on these tools to monitor progress, make informed decisions, and collaborate effectively. Their active involvement throughout the development process, including providing feedback, testing the dashboards, and suggesting improvements, is crucial for the successful implementation and adoption of the dashboards.

In specific situations, other actors may be involved in the process, such as:

Data Providers: Data providers are individuals or teams responsible for collecting and managing the data that will be visualized on the dashboards. They may include researchers, data analysts, laboratory technicians, and other project personnel. Data providers play a vital role in ensuring that the necessary data is collected, validated, and prepared for integration into the dashboards. Their collaboration is essential for data integration and quality assurance.

As already explained, although the implementation of the dashboards is a labor-intensive activity, it is expected to have several impacts on the project's implementation conditions and on the shared governance, such as:

Improved Decision-Making: The dashboards provide stakeholders with timely, accurate, and actionable insights. This enables more informed decision-making at various levels within the project. Stakeholders can track progress, identify bottlenecks, and make data-driven decisions to optimize resources, address challenges, and align efforts with strategic objectives. This leads to improve project management and outcomes.

Enhanced Collaboration and Communication: The dashboards facilitate collaboration and communication among project participants. Stakeholders can easily access and share information, monitor the progress of collaborations, and identify opportunities for synergies. This fosters a collaborative environment, encourages knowledge exchange, and strengthens partnerships, ultimately improving the project's implementation conditions.

Resource Optimization: The dashboards provide visibility into the utilization of facilities, tools, services, and resources within the project. Stakeholders can identify underutilized or overutilized resources, optimize resource allocation, and ensure efficient utilization. This leads to better resource management, cost savings, and improved operational efficiency.

Increased Accountability and Transparency: The dashboards promote accountability by providing transparent and accessible information about project activities, progress, and outcomes. Stakeholders can track performance against predefined metrics and KPIs, monitor the impact of strategic initiatives, and evaluate the effectiveness of collaborations. This fosters

transparency, fosters a culture of accountability, and enhances the project's implementation conditions.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This deliverable is intended to represent a practical resource to understand and consolidate the project's acquired knowledge, offering valuable support to the Project decision-making structure in achieving project objectives (Shared Goals) and monitor Key Activities needed to deliver (timely and on budget) Key Exploitable Results as a tangible outcome. D1.5 provides a comprehensive assessment of the implementation conditions ("the path from Shared Goals to Key Exploitable Results [...] defining Key Activities") of the project.

Based on the Project's structure, and in consideration of the related Shared Goals, Key Activities and Key Exploitable Results, the report evaluates various thematic issues, such as the activities of the Research Infrastructures (RIs) nodes, policy compliance, partnerships and networking, facility management, strategic development, and activities evaluation. The findings highlight the importance of effective coordination, collaboration, and adherence to guidelines for the successful realization of the project's objectives (Shared Goals).

After clarifying the purpose and objectives of the deliverable and the crucial role played by Task 1.5 in the process of setting up the optimal conditions to provide practical assistance to the decision-making structure of the H2IOSC project, the document proposes to promote the design of a centralized data platform, providing real-time insights into various aspects of the project's implementation and outcomes, allowing stakeholders, including the Project decision-making structure, to monitor the project's performance against predetermined targets (i.e.: Shared Goals), as part of Task 1.5 activities.

Furthermore, a methodology, including indications on assessing implementation conditions (i.e.: "the path from Shared Goals to Key Exploitable Results") and recommendations on data collection and analysis methods are proposed. Eventually, with the aim of designing and implementing specific tools (i.e. Dashboards) to monitor "the path from Shared Goals to Key Exploitable Results", leveraging on existing monitoring and reporting tools, processes and systems and reducing the fragmentation of the current situation, a set of tools (Dashboards) to be considered as examples, to be refined through collaborative design within the project has been proposed.

Specific recommendations mentioned in the report for further improvements include:

1. **Strengthening Infrastructure Node Performance:** Enhancing the performance of the Research Infrastructures (RIs) nodes by leveraging advanced technologies and tools, ensuring efficient data management, and promoting collaboration.
2. **Ensuring Policy and Guideline Compliance:** Implementing a Policy and Guideline Compliance Dashboard to monitor and ensure adherence to established policies and guidelines, promoting transparency and accountability within the project.
3. **Enhancing Partnership and Networking:** Developing a Partnership and Networking Performance Dashboard to foster collaborations with relevant actors, such as other

research infrastructures, institutions, and stakeholders, thereby expanding the project's reach and impact.

4. **Effective Management of Facilities, Tools, and Services:** Establishing a Facilities, Tools, and Services Management Dashboard to streamline the coordination and management of project resources, ensuring their availability, accessibility, and proper utilization.
5. **Strategic Development and Collaboration:** Creating a Strategic Development and Collaboration Dashboard to facilitate the formulation and implementation of strategic documents, such as business models and technology transfer plans, promoting effective networking and knowledge exchange.
6. **Performance Measurement and Assessment:** Implementing a Performance Measurement and Assessment Dashboard to monitor and assess the project's progress, identifying areas of improvement, and ensuring the achievement of project goals and objectives.

5. Updates and Continuous Monitoring

D1.5 outlines the plan for monitoring the H2IOSC project. It provides an updated state of the project at the end of October 2025, including the proposed solutions to address the identified issues with details regarding the current implementation of the tools to ensure the continuous monitoring of H2IOSC implementation conditions.

It also provides the values to populate the dashboards so to have a complete view of H2IOSC implementation.

The information collected is useful to track the progress of the project, assess the effectiveness of the proposed solutions, and provide opportunities for improvement. This approach fosters a dynamic and responsive project environment and facilitates the implementation of necessary improvements. Indeed, these data, on the one hand, help in making some adjustments for the successful completion of the project, on the other hand, they provide important elements for reflection in setting the medium-long term strategy of the H2IOSC cluster.